

HYCOOL-IT

HYBRID COOLING & MANAGEMENT
FOR IT INFRASTRUCTURES

<https://hycoolit-project.eu/>

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Introduction

HYCOOL-IT will develop a new set of replicable and cost-effective solutions for a better understanding of the challenges in thermal management of IT Server Rooms. This includes increased open knowledge regarding Digital Twin methodological and ICT solutions focused on the tertiary buildings, ready to be replicated in the most common specific use cases across EU. From the technical equipment point of view, the project also targets a best- of-class adsorption modular solution to recover and valorise excess heat.

The Problem

Hycool_IT intends to develop and demonstrate the feasibility to generate and upkeep a Digital Twin of both the IT Server Room and the whole Building.

Electricity consumption of Server Rooms in tertiary buildings constituted a significant share of the total energy consumption in finance and public offices, and it was estimated at 4% of the electricity demand in the EU27+2 tertiary sector. Such demand has been growing in recent years and is expected to grow even more, following the increasing trend for the total EU electricity consumption of data centers. Many companies, school districts, hospitals, and universities are increasingly requiring bigger Server Rooms included in their premises to provide support of their critical Information Technology (IT) applications, as well as the smart managing of the asset itself.

The Solution

Project's general objectives

The purpose of HYCOOL-IT is to develop a set of processes supported by both digital and technical equipment innovative solutions for an efficient and reliable development of IT Server Rooms for advanced tertiary buildings, with a special focus on its replicability through standardisation. In parallel, a highly innovative Rack-integrated adsorption chiller for waste-heat powered server cooling is developed and optimized to carry out efficient liquid cooling of IT servers and, simultaneously, provide cooling to the server room itself in a compact, self-contained, and cost-effective way.

The Building Digital Twin Environment (BDTE) will be developed as a PaaS with their specific Web API communication microservices to connect specific tools to support planning and design assessment, commissioning and performance evaluation processes including advanced technical equipment solutions digitalized through as BDT SimBOTs (interactive simulators) in the ICT Ecosystem to enable a more effective integration and operation of these advanced server rooms within the whole buildings.

Moreover, SimBOTS pave the way for the future prescription of the innovative technical equipment proposed in the project. In addition, existing rooms can be mirrored and enhanced with the usage of BDT Environments to generate improved baselines and forecasting to support designers in the design phase, choosing the best design option and for maintenance engineers to enable performance contracting to realise the KPI's.

Specific objectives and technological applications

New innovative solutions requirements will be considered to properly implement hybrid systems for cooling through the recovery of waste heat produced by the IT Rooms contained in tertiary buildings, including the use of the new components proposed like the plugin rack integrated adsorption chillers.

The project will pursue the development of an ICT ecosystem and orchestration software solutions for the evaluation of software interoperability among the potential results expected in the project at TRL3 level on this research to show that implementing IoT and other smart elements to contribute to build HYCOOL-IT ecosystems and contribute to promote data-driven decisions in tertiary buildings among decision-makers, building administrators, and other stakeholders. The implementation of IoT ecosystems and its orchestration through different tools and functions, should be economically viable and environmentally sustainable since it introduces very low environmental costs (both operational and embedded) resulting from the waste heat valorisation (to produce cooling or to integrated in the heating services networks).

Impacts

Innovative solutions for an efficient and reliable development of IT Server Rooms for advanced tertiary buildings, with a special focus on its replicability through standardisation. In parallel, a highly innovative Rack-integrated adsorption chiller for waste-heat powered server cooling is developed and optimized to carry out efficient liquid cooling of IT servers and, simultaneously, provide cooling to the server room itself in a compact, self-contained, and cost-effective way.

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